

Passions of mortals and immortals. Variegated love making pervading Nature and forms of life. Wars fought. Rise and fall of mighty warriors. Men and gods taking sides. Death, destruction and a desolate battlefield where vultures prey on bodies of heroes whose souls have ascended heaven. The most profound thought on life, death and emancipation transmitted in a battlefield on the eve of a war in which protagonists and antagonists are kinsfolk ready to strike at one another. Gita from a Teacher who is God (Krishna) Himself. The great gambler whose passion for gambling is the road to liberation. One who plays dice with life, wife, brothers and himself. Who in the end discovers that liberation is gambling away the temptation to liberation. The meeting of Heaven and Earth. The heavenly Ganga flowing down the earth to redeem dead souls from the ashes. The Central Hero's ascent to Heaven only to discover that the cosmic order is not and cannot be disturbed. That The Great War or Mahabharata had been only a virtual reality to drive home this penultimate point.

In all these, three strands, namely, sex, violence and liberation, constitute the thread weaving the units into a garland. The structure and units share the same symmetry.

It has been well said that whatever is to be found, is found in the Mahabharata. And whatever is not found in the Mahabharata, is not to be found, elsewhere. Perhaps the subtle hint is that Mahabharata draws its cultural boundaries and continues to do so. Many scholars believe that the Mahabharata-Manipur metaphor is a classic example of expansive redrawing of cultural map. Some argue, as sloppily as arguments can be, that the Mahabharata-Manipur² is

² On the identification of Mahabharata Manipur, all hitherto advanced arguments are based on classical methods of reading and interpreting the Puranas. These classical methods do not show us the difference between myth and history, fact and metaphor. A new method of interpretation founded on following the morphology of meaning is needed. In the present

the present State of India called Manipur – a once sovereign kingdom forcibly annexed to the Dominion of India on 15 October, 1949 (see, Sanajaoba, 1988; 1993; Haobam, 1988; Aheibam et. al., 2014; Menon, 2016). Giving this proposition as premise to themselves, they gleefully conclude that crystallisations of cultural boundaries into political boundaries are the logical thing to follow. No wonder, they say, the transformation of Mahabharata-Manipur metaphor into a political entity called the State of Manipur within the Union of India, is a master stroke.³

I am not entering into the above debate of identification for reasons known to any scholar seriously engaged with the historiography of Manipur. My engagement will be more modest. I will simply try to explore the layers of meaning of the Mahabharata- Manipur metaphor keeping myself within the bounds of archaeology of meaning. I will also try to draw the conclusions these meanings entail. Fidelity to the Mahabharata text will be an essential part of my methodology.

2. Birth of Heroes: Why, How and Whereabouts

In the Mahabharata, birth is a mode of embodiment entered into by cosmic forces, material and spiritual – a crystallisation of their configuration. Sexual reproduction is not the only way of embodiment. Thus, Draupadi takes her

essay, I have tried to develop such an archaeology of meaning and use it for interpreting the Mahabharata text. Consistently applied, this method dissolves the Manipur Mahabharata identification problem.

³ This is the position of the newly emerging Manipuri middle class who became active and joined the winning Congress bandwagon in the late 1940s and 1950s. The great leader Hijam Irawat is the lone star in the political firmament of Manipur who led the people during this tumultuous period and thus became a beacon light for all time to follow.

embodiment as an enigmatic entity coming out of fire (Chingganbam, 1956b: 765-770). A perfect Beauty! A riddle, revenge and therefore a challenge! To receive her beauty – one must be able to see “that beauty” in the deluge of blood called Mahabharata-Dharmakshetra-Kurukshetra where God and men fight together for righteousness in the vindication of a wounded feminine self. Draupadi is the epic heroine precisely because she cause it to happen by a starkly naked vow to let loose at large her wildly flowing hairs till they are washed and purified in Dushasana’s blood. Protagonists and antagonists are to swim their ways through in this ocean of blood to be called heroes.

Karna’s embodiment or the becoming of what Karna is; is already destined in the cruel superbly designed joke that Durvasha played on Kunti while she is yet a tender but beautiful virgin. This fiery but farsighted (?) Brahmin vouchsafed the young virgin a Mantra-power to call any god who will be glad to be seduced by her beauty and impregnate her. Curiosity, perhaps not without longing, arouses her to call Surya Deva, the Sun god, the source of light and life. He appears, eager to make love and fulfil the purpose embedded in the Mantra power. Kunti regrets, imploring Surya to forgive a young virgin’s bold innocence. But this coy refusal for Surya is rather a foreplay! The god is already aroused; intensely desiring union with her in love. He tells her that Durvasha’s Mantra goes along with a boon to receive a progeny from the Divine Being to whom the mantra is addressed. Therefore, the user of the Mantra is destined to celebrate the union of love with the god so invoked. To this Kunti’s remonstrations is; how can a virgin make love and be with a child, without transgressing Dharma. The Sun god’s counter assurance is she will have her child instantly, while at the same time keeping her virginity intact (Chingganbam, 1956a:284-285; Chingganbam, 1956b:528-529; Chingganbam, 1962a:232-238). Thus persuaded, virgin Kunti and the amorously warm Surya celebrate their union of love in solitude. The fruition is our tragic hero Karna destined to set in the darkness of the Dharmakshetra-Kurukshetra called Mahabharata. Surya’s ray penetrating the Virgin but keeping her maidenhood intact climaxing in Karna’s embodiment arising out of the Sun god’s energy transcends limits of imagination. This, quite apart from considerations of possibilities within the frontiers of biology! (Chingganbam, 1962b:238-287). Here, aesthetic elegance is god, men and nature conspire to “let there be a Karna

and lo! Our hero arrives”. The ethical elegance is, the hero is challenged to exercise his choice at every critical stage, whereas in reality, even the Kierkegaardian Either/Or alternatives are never provided. Nevertheless, Karna makes shaping a destiny of self-destruction, his choice (a Kierkegaardian Lily all over again). The metaphysical beauty is, Karna’s “thrownness” (in the Heideggerian jargon) in the world – abandonment complete and self-sufficient in itself. The resplendent hero of the highest warrior caste is condemned to masquerade as a lowly Sudra. I deliberately use the word masquerade because the making of Karna-destiny unfolds a profound paradox at the bottom of becoming a Hindu, which is as follows.

The genetic engineer of Karna-destiny is the far seeing (?) Brahmin Durvasha whose strategy is upholding the eternal order of Varna hierarchy of Brahmanic dominance. The seed is the mantra he gives Kunti. The catalyst is Kunti’s curiosity to see how the mantra works – a curiosity not unmixed with an innocently unconscious maidenly desire. The fruition is, beginning of Karna-destiny from the union of god and virgin. The motif weaving the texture we call tragic Karna-destiny is the overriding ideology of Varna Dharma elevated to a metaphysical principle of eternal cosmic order. One can call this ideology Brahmanism, the rule of the game is Brahmins on the top position. No Sudra ought not and/or cannot aspire to the brand of excellence accruing to a Brahmin by caste. For, excellence belongs not to a universal human essence, but to an insulated segment of a highly structured system. The system is not only unchanging and stratified arrogating ontological dignity of eternity to itself, but also self-justifying. The very presence of the system is the necessary and sufficient condition of its rational justification. The certainty is one of “I am, therefore, I am the Truth”. For the author of Mahabharata, Karna’s appearance in the cosmic history is to prove that a Sudra can never become a Kshatriya, save by default or proxy. Therefore, if one fine morning you find a Sudra appearing in a contending arena or battlefield donning splendour and demeanour of a Kshatriya, check the pedigree and you will

invariably find a Kshatriya one. A Sudra has no merit or excellence intrinsically endowed upon him by virtue of being human. Which means caste is thicker than human essence. This Brahmanic truth extends further. Once you have been positioned as a Sudra in Varna fold, your return to a higher caste is foreclosed, even if the return is a formal one only. This explains Karna's dignified "No" to Kunti's invitation to join and head the Pandava fold. Also, the paradox at the heart of being a Hindu within the Brahmanic fold. One's caste need not necessarily guarantee one's humanity. Conversely, one's humanity need not guarantee one's caste. And when a Hindu is asked to sustain both caste and humanity together within the fold he needs an original position from where the choice is to be made. Such an original position however is not given within the fold. Asking for it will tantamount to leaving the fold. So, a Hindu has the freedom of choice only and only when he no longer needs it or to put it the other way, the Brahmanic fold no longer needs his being a Hindu. Karna's unfoldment as an epic hero is a running commentary on this paradox at the heart of the Brahmanic Hindu world. Even Kunti's own positioning of herself vis-à-vis Karna speaks volumes on this paradox. Her positioning, from the very beginning is more political than motherly. For Karna, his birth is his own defeat. He is epic hero of the highest order because he consciously chooses to prove "this defeat" in the encircling darkness of the Mahabharata war. Mahabharata poignantly asks; whose defeat? whose victory? Your answer will tell which side of the barricade you are in.

In the Mahabharata, Yudhistira is the Tree of Righteousness (Dharma) (Chingganbam, 1956a: 8). The tree has as its basis, Krishna, who is Personal God and Impersonal Brahman at one stroke. Yudhistira's brothers, Bhima, Arjuna, Sahadeva and Nakula are the organic parts. The five Pandava brother's descent on earth is to serve the cause of Dharma (righteousness) by waging a righteous war against the dark forces of Adharma (unrighteousness). Each of them is a human embodiment of one or the other forces (personalised by a divine being or god) the

sum totality of which constitute the cosmic order. Thus Yudhistira is born of Yama's (God of Dharma) seed, Bhima of Vayu's (God of Air i.e., strength), Arjuna of Indra's (King of gods, the rain god wielding thunderbolt) – sown in Kunti's womb. Birth and making of heroes in the Mahabharata, thus, is part of a cosmic process. The womb, the owner of the womb, the seed, the originator of the seed and the cosmic force personalised in the origination, the motif of planting the seed, how configuration of forces at that moment of cosmic history is designed, position of the heavenly bodies in constellation etc. – all these are vibrating movements in the grand design of upholding the cosmic order.

Yudhistira is the epic hero of Mahabharata. He is character-at-the-centre, Kendriya Purusha. Metaphysical problematic of righteousness are raised and resolved centering around him and him only. This is so, because, above everything Yudhistira is a passionate being. His great gambling away of brothers, wife Draupadi and finally himself is a passionate act, following the dictates of the heart. At the same time, it is also an act of faith in which everything, most of all oneself, is put at stake apart from rational considerations of the consequences. It is not a saintly act. It is a humane, soulful act welling up from the heart having its own reasons. Saints are qualified for heaven but not emancipation. Only passionate human beings are qualified to be epic heroes and be emancipated. In his encounter with Yaksha who is none other than God of Dharma himself, Yudhistira displays soulful knowledge of cosmic order and commitment to Sanatana Dharma—also sense of fairness in his desire for restoring life to Nakula, younger brother from step mother Madri's womb. In the purported Pandava ascent to Heaven, it is Yudhistira alone who scales the mountainous heights and enters Heaven in person by his passionate yet humane act of gambling away the very chance of entering Heaven. He proves that he is the one who will not enter Heaven without his dog following him faithfully—a dog who is none other than the God of Dharma himself in guise; this

time again. These three critical but passionate authentic existential choices position Yudhistira at the centre of the epic, making him the Kendriya Purusha.

We know Arjuna, Indra's gift to Pandu sown in Kunti's womb, as Krishna's disciple to whom the Lord gave Gita at the Kurukshetra battlefield where protagonists and antagonists are arrayed to strike at one another. Arjuna is the repository of immortal words of the Lord, flowing down to humanity forever. "To fight or not to fight—where is the reason?" makes Arjuna a hero, perhaps in the sense of a privileged disciple who now knows his ways about in the battlefield of Mahabharata. Enough to make him a hero but not an epic hero! An epic hero carries not only wisdom but, also passion. The reason to wage the Mahabharata war is Krishna's which is why we have the Gita. Yudhistira's passion for righteousness and Draupadi's passion for revenge is the driving force, passion sustaining the war throughout. Arjuna does the fighting. In Draupadi's Swayambara, Arjuna's concentration in piercing the fish-eye with his arrow makes him a hero. He is enamoured with Draupadi but lacks a full blooded passion as subsequent events show. His fight with God Mahadeva reveals incredible prowess and warrior's skill, but lacks Abhimanyu's epic destiny of fighting through the Chakravihyu. His rejection of Urvashi's advances is puzzling. More so, when to be seduced by a beautiful woman is in the fabric of an epic hero's destiny. Urvashi, of whom the Mahabharata poet says that on the way to meet Arjun her beautiful bounty breasts moving ahead of time pull the body forward while the weight of her gently curved solid hips is slowing down making her glide like a coy eager woman, is neither bound nor related to anybody. An ageless Apsara that she is, Urvashi's beautiful form is not for any mortal to be profaned. Hers is the destiny to seduce heroes, connoisseurs of beauty and aspirants who undertake penance for supernatural power to dethrone Indra. Ironically, it is this same Pandava hero Arjuna who falls for Chitrangada, the princess of Manipur, giving rise to the problematics centering around, what I call the Manipur Mahabharata metaphor.

3. The Ownership of Womb and Naming

The doctrine of womb ownership and naming is to be understood before we proceed to the problematics of Mahabharata Manipur metaphor. Not only this. We must also have a graphic intimacy with the politics of womb ownership and naming as laid out in the Mahabharata.

He who owns the womb owns the fruit no matter whose seed it is. The way of the world is for the owner to plant his own seed in the womb he owns. When the seed grows into the tree of life, the implanting owner ensures immortality of his ancestors and his own also. He does so by positioning himself as a link in the continuity that extends to the past and the future.

In his “present” he lives his ancestors. At the same time, he lives his “present” in the future possibilities as realised by his progeny. His “present” therefore, is a microcosm carrying the seed of past present- future macrocosm which constitutes a totalising continuity. The owner of the womb who sows a seed therein, transforming himself into a link in the continuum is upholding Dharma, the way to immortality. Here, we have a convergence point of biological reproduction, material production, the creation of culture and upholding of Dharma.

The Mahabharata doctrine also gives the way of Dharma to an owner of a womb to plant a seed other than his own in the womb he owns. When the owner’s power or ability to plant the seed of life is circumscribed by impotency curse or untimely death, Dharmic imperative to uphold the continuum of cosmic order empowers

him or his representative kins to take recourse to the Dharmic way of planting seed (Chingganbam, 1956a: 289). The imperative is on him or his representative to cause implantation of seed in the womb he owns, from a venerable source mortal or immortal (Chingganbam, 1956a: 502-507; Soyam, 2017: 418-429). Following this Dharmic imperative, Bhishma and mother Satyawati cause birth of Dhritarashtra, Pandu and Vidura from Shree Krishna-Dwaipayana- Veda Vyasa's seeds implanted in the wombs of Ambika, Ambalika and Ambalika's maid servant respectively. As Vichitravirya's widows their wombs belong to him and him alone. So are the fruits sown in their wombs. They are to inherit the lineage of King Shantanu and his great ancestors (Chingganbam, 1956a: 510-514). The cursed Pandu likewise is to be blessed with Yudhishtira from Yama's seed, Bhima from Vayu's and Arjuna's from Indra's—all planted in Kunti's womb. Nakula and Sahadeva are boons from Ashwinikumar planted in Madri's womb. Although the five sons are fruits from variegated venerable seeds, they are to be called Pandavas or sons of Pandu (Chingganbam, 1956b: 568-584). Their patriarchal lineage or family tree is to be traced to Pandu and his ancestors. No matter whose seed they are, they are owned by the owner of the wombs from where they blossom forth as tree of life. Pandu indisputably, is the Dharmic father of the five brothers to whom the generic name Pandava is given. At this point the Mahabharata advances a bold thesis. One may even call it a challenge for engagement in thought experiment. The thesis is that this Dharmic way of begetting son to uphold the totalising continuum of cosmic order we have described above, neither contradicts the freedom of choice nor the marital fidelity of the characters and catalysing agents concerned. Here is an ethical, metaphysical and psycho-analytical problematic exploration of which will be such an irresistible temptation. It is impossible for me to succumb to this temptation within the boundaries of this paper. I can only hope that future holds out possibilities for me. I will therefore proceed to the other ramification of the womb ownership doctrine, namely, the doctrine of naming.

He who owns the womb owns the fruit arising thereof. He who owns the fruit owns the power and legitimacy to name the fruit. Naming gives you a mystical power over the things you name. Therefore, naming is how you keep on expanding your power over the thing world. Naming is how you draw the boundaries of the world again and again. The moment land is considered an extension of a woman's womb to be used by the owner for material production you have a fusion of womb ownership doctrine and land ownership doctrine. Given that inheritance of naming power is through the male line, the emerging holistic doctrine leads to a patriarchal state formation doctrine of ever expanding womb ownership and land ownership. The first form of expansion is the root-cause of demographic war. The second is the root-cause of war for territorial expansion. Here I am only working out the tragic consequences of apparently innocent doctrines.

4. The Mahabharata-Manipur Metaphor: A Paradigm Shift

Arjuna is on a self-imposed exile for what he considers to be a violation of the code of husbanding Draupadi agreed upon by the five brothers. In his wanderings he arrives at the land of Naga Princess Ulupi, daughter Naga King Kaurabya of Eirabot dynasty. While Arjuna is taking bath in the river, Ulupi finds him. She is sexually excited and drags down Arjuna to her palace underneath the water. Her proposal to Arjuna is for instant sexual union. Her argument is; she is still unmarried and therefore has freedom of sexual union with whomsoever she likes. Her second argument is that they are now in solitude, an ideal moment for love making. Her third argument is that she is overwhelmed with desire for sexual union (Chingganbam, 1956b: 942-945).

Arjuna's rejoinder to Ulupi's argument is that he is bound by a vow of celibacy. How can he satisfy her without transgressing his vow? To this Ulupi's reply is the frame of reference of the vow is the Pandava brothers and Draupadi only. As such, it does not apply to her relation with the Pandava hero. She also adds that if he fails to satisfy her desire, she will give up her life. The curse will then on his head for not saving a woman. Arjuna surrenders and they unite in love. Here the Mahabharata text is making the point that a moral code practised in a given context, place and environment is not necessarily applicable in a different context, place and environment. Arjuna, therefore, is morally free from his self-imposed vow of celibacy.

From Ulupi's palace, crossing Kalinga Desh Arjuna arrives at the Kingdom of Manipur whose King is Chitrabahan, a devout monarch. His daughter Chitrangada is a perfect beauty. The Pandava hero is overwhelmed by her beauty. He goes to her father King Chitrabahan. Introducing himself as a Kshatriya of the highest order, that is, Pandu's son born of Kunti's womb, Arjuna begs of the King her daughter Chitrangada's hand in marriage (Chingganbam, 1956b:946-948).

Now we arrive at the most critical point which is the major thrust of my paper. The point simply is King Chitrabahan's counter proposal to Arjuna. The King tells Arjuna that his daughter Chitrangada is his only begotten child. As he has no son, Chitrangada is the only one who can continue the clan lineage. She therefore is an embodiment of both son and daughter for the King. In reality, she has been installed as "Putrika Putra", the "Daughter-Son" of the King's clan in accordance with Shastraicritual-ceremonies. Therefore, if a son is born of Chitrangada's womb, he is to be a patriarch, a King in this context, of King Chitrabahan's clan. He cannot be a male member of the Pandava clan. Arjuna can marry Chitrangada if and only if, this proposition is acceptable to him (Chingganbam, 1956b: 946-948).

Arjuna gives his assent to Chitrabahan's terms and conditions. He marries Chitrangada, staying in the palace for three years. A son, who is to become famous as Babrubahan, is born of Chitrangada's womb. However, he is to remain as Chitrangada's son and Chitrabahan's grandson; subsequently King of Manipur. The Mahabharata textual point is crystal clear. Arjuna marries Chitrangada but never owns her womb. She herself is the owner of her womb. Therefore, even if the seed is from Arjuna, institutionally Babrubahan is her son and he belongs to her clan. Never to the Pandava clan.

This point is confirmed in Arjuna's second encounter with his son Babrubahan, now King of Manipur, while following the Ashwamedha horse. His refusal to recognise Babrubahan as his son, calling him a bastard, is insistence on the womb ownership doctrine. So is his dubious forgetfulness of the original terms and conditions of marriage with Chitrangada. The outraged Babrubahan killing Arjuna in the ensuing battle is a metaphor of resistance to the womb ownership doctrine. Ulupi's intervention of restoring Arjuna's life represents a point of equilibrium in between two radically different doctrines and cultures (Chingganbam, 1989: 92-108).

The greatness of Mahabharata lies not only in the truth that the epic draws its own boundaries, but also in the consciousness anticipated centuries ago that drawing cultural boundaries has its own limits.

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